

Title and Details

a.Title

Faris' Theory of Special Relativity Probabilism-Challenging the Einstein's Special Relativity Theory

b.Author Information

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c.Note

It is requested to please pay attention because I want Reserach Team to work on some Concepts on which I am working .I have some Associate Professors at Lahore which are helping me with my concepts but complete Research Team is needed. Mathematical derivations of only this theory is a so difficult task that it will need quantum computer and I am also not mathematically very expert but I can show everything in this paper mathematically if I get enough knowledge and a Research Team.I am Mirza Faris Ahmad. I was Independent Reseracher. The Concepts on which I am working are:

1.Theory of Special String-Probabilism (a Theory that can potentially challenge Special Relativity Probabilism),Theory of Special Superposition String-Probabilism(a Theory that can potentially challenge Special String-Probabilism), General version of Theory of String-Probabilism ,Theory of Relativity Probabilism and Theory of Superposition String-Probabilism are also under Research.

2.Precendeces of Theories By Multiple Velocities.

3.Group Theory Right Precendence Prediction.

4.Adding Uncertainties in group theory prediction to get situation dependent theories.

5.Theory of Everything based on

(1) Fluctuative Dark Matter And Energy with Spacetime and Ether as Reference Quantities

(2)Dark Matter and Energy

(3)Ether

(4)Gravitational Superposition

(5)Vaccum

(6)Spacetime

6.Dark-Spacetime1-Ether Fluctuation Model (Models are based on particles and replace the theories which are based on Concept like absolute,relative etc)

7.Precendences for Models by Multiple particles

8.Number Theory Right Precendence Prediction of Models

9.Adding uncertainties in Number Theory Right Precendence Prediction to get situation dependent models.

10.Modeled Everything Theory Based on “Dark-Spacetime1-Ether Fluctuation”

11.Combined Outdevised Physics and Indevised Physics Modeled Everything Theory Based on

“Dark-Spacetime1-Ether Fluctuation”

12.I already have a Prove to show that the Fundamental Forces of Nature all have their sources and they are not Fundamental.

13.I have more advance concept than Quantum Computers called Fluctuative Bits With Different notation which Highlights existence of Fluctuative Computers of Different Interfaces and also Fluctuative Qubits which Highlights existence of Fluctuative Quantum Computers.

14.I have Classify science on the basis of Devise in two types called Indevised Science and Outdevised Science. I am also looking forward to classify science on other different basis.

15.Every Permutation and Combination of theories can be made and on any concept a theory can be made ,the general results for these are also under Research.

16.New Concept of Dark Matter and Dark Energy based on many different things.

Short Summary

Universe is not so simple.Every object is formed depending upon the particles' probabilities or waves coherence which make it. Problems in

Newton's and Einstein's theory are resolved by using new theory whose postulates are explained. Prediction and New Transformation Equations are presented using the postulates. Mathematical derivations of this theory is a so difficult task that it will need quantum computer and I am also not mathematically very expert but I can show everything in this paper mathematically if I get enough knowledge and a Research Team. This is a Theory based on Relative Probabilism. Absolute informally means one body with its physical quantities(the only one reference frame that can have changing spacetime coordinates or fixed spacetime coordinates or simply any changing or fixed physical quantity,this is explained in "What is Absolute?" in article) in spacetime while relative means two bodies with their physical quantities(the two reference frames that can have changing spacetime coordinates or fixed spacetime coordinates or simply any changing or fixed physical quantity,this is explained in "What is Relative?" in article) in spacetime which can theoretically go to n bodies therefore the concept of relative in Relative Probabilism is much different from traditional one so on the basis of traditional relative and absolute there can be other probabilism theories by considering spacetime as independent. Since New atomic Model (described in Probabilism's Foundation) shows matter as a resultant of spacetime hence now definition of Absolute and Relative changes for Probability which highlights deviation of this relative from traditional one. This also solves Sixth Problem mentioned in article. Now Yes there can be a Theory of Absolute Probabilism and yes these Probabilism theories can also go to n bodies. This is the Problem again.

The Keywords

- 1.Theory to replace Relativity
- 2.New Transformation Equations
- 3.Quantum Theory
- 4.Relativity and Probability
- 5.Waves and Particles distinction

Statements and Declarations

a.Competing Interests

No, I declare that the authors have no competing interests as defined by Springer, or other interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper.

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c.Author Contribution

I am Mirza Faris Ahmad .The only Author and Researcher of this Research Paper.

The Theory

Introduction

Universe is not so simple.Every object is formed depending upon the particles' probabilities or waves coherence(coherence can also be in intermediate states) which make it.

The Problems and Solutions

What is Absolute?

Absolute quantities means to compare a body's any physical quantity in its reference frame with respect to a same physical quantity in universal frame of reference now clearly their are two reference frame in spacetime the difference is that one is fixed in spacetime and other can be considered fixed in spacetime and can also be considered to change in spacetime(due to changing space and time coordinates or simply change in any physical quantity) depending on given situation.

What is Relative?

Relative quantities means to compare a body's any physical quantity in its reference frame with respect to a same physical quantity in another frame of reference now clearly their are again two reference frame in spacetime in which no difference is present here because both can be considered fixed in spacetime and can also be considered to change in spacetime(due to changing spacetime coordinates or simply change in any physical quantity) depending on given situation.

Note

1.Correct Meaning of Absolute and Relative are given

Above is the correct elaboration of the concept of Absolute and Relative which is used in Today's World. Clearly **Absolute is a special case of Relative** because when one reference frame become fixed in spacetime relative becomes absolute.

2. Mathematical statement

The following is a mathematical statement

“If Laws of Physics were different for different observers in Relative motion then observers can find from this difference which of them is stationary in space and which of them is moving but such a distinction does not exist so Laws of Physics are the same.”

This is because it shows that by applying lorentz transformation equations for velocity between two reference frames, laws will be the same.

Problem in Newton's and Einstein's Theory

Problem: 1 Einstein First Postulate says that laws are same and also different

Consider the same sentence “If Laws of Physics were different for different observers in Relative motion then observers can find from this difference which of them is stationary in space and which of them is moving but such a distinction does not exist so Laws of Physics are same”.

Now write this in two ways

1. If Laws of Physics were different for different observers in Relative motion then observers can find from this difference which of them is stationary in space and which of them is moving but such a distinction does not exist so Laws of Physics are same.

2. If Laws of Physics were different for different observers in Relative motion then observers can find from this difference which of them is stationary in space and which of them is moving but such a distinction does not exist so lets relate their state of rest and motion so the difference in laws is because of relative motion.

Now I use the Words to manipulate the math to show that laws can differ by the same lorentz equations.

Problem: 2 Exception to Relativity Postulates

Relativity postulates breakdown at certain points.

Principle of Relativity has Exception

Method 1 Conservation Laws

Consider the New Atomic model (described in Probablistism's Foundation) and the basic Physical quantities which are mass, charge and velocity etc what this means is that there individual conservation laws exists in Quantum physics but when the resultant quantities obtained by their combination like momentum, kinetic energy etc they will have although their conservation laws but if one will combine all the resultant quantities conservation laws there combined conservation laws with these basic physical quantity will not be a conservation law hence laws of Physics indeed change when you **move from Quantum scale to Classical Scale.**

Rough Example

Clearly their can be infinitely possible quantities by these fundamental physical quantities and there can be infinte conservation laws which will combine and when represented in fundamental quantities it will show that law of conservation of mass is breaking down since energy is increasing. **Laws are changing** while moving from Quantum scale to Classical Scale.

Method 2 Certain Important Probabilities

When certain probabilities dominate in **Probablistism's Foundation** to create some specific object then some situations can be created where laws of physics will be different.

Constancy of Light Speed has Exception

Wave and Particle are two different aspects of one reality and they must not be mixed according to Probablistism's Foundation. Although they are coexisting at quantum state described by wavefunction which can either collapses to particle or to wave upon measurement but this does not mean to use the wave properties laws on particles and particle properties laws on wave. Although this is being done today but the problem is that the mathematical laws are different for wave and particles which gives same physical meaning so the same physical meaning of experiments allows to make a mathematical law that can be valid for both particle properties and wave properties.

Now Use the EM field to accelerate the Speed of Light when light is behaving as EM Wave by using Transformation Equations of Faris' Theory of Special Relativity Probabilism.

Problem: 3 Einstein First postulate Violation

Galilean Relativity is also a law and it is not valid in reference frame of michelson morley experiment but valid in other reference frames like light speed in train although experiment shows same result but Law is different Theoretically.

Problem: 4 Einstein First Postulate Violated by Second

As Speed of Light is constant in all reference frames but not in Galilean Relativity reference frame then Laws of Physics are not same. Second Postulate is also a Law that Speed of Light is Constant, this law is changing first postulate violated by second.

Problem: 5 Need and No Need of Einstein Second Postulate

Speed of Light increases or decreases in Galilean Relativity but not in Michelson Morley Experiment so there is exception to first postulate which cause second postulate. Second postulate is also a law so why it is needed since it is described in postulate one that laws of physics are same.

Problem: 6 Universal Reference Frame

Spacetime in the actual meaning of Absolute and Relative which I described above can be Considered as a Universal Frame of reference hence highlighting problem in Concept of Absolute and Relative.

Problem: 7 The Blackmail Physics Loop

Because Laws of Physics are same therefore speed of light is found out to be constant and since speed of light is constant, laws of physics are same.

Combined Solution

Theory of Special Relativity Probabilism with its three postulates can solve these problems in Newton's and Einstein's Theory.

Postulate:1 Principle of Probabilism

Laws of Physics are Probabilistic and can be different.

Explanation

Laws of Physics are not same in probabilistic reference frames because it will depend on relative probabilistic measurements of probabilistic reference frames of particles.

Postulate:2 Relative Probabilistism

The Probabilistic Quantities in New Atomic Model(described by Probabilistism's Foundation) have their own Probabilistic Reference frames which are relative for each probabilistic quantity of each Relativistic Probabilistic Particle.

Meaning of Relative Probabilistism

Relative Probabilistism quantities means to compare a relativistic probabilistic particle's any probabilistic physical quantity in its probabilistic reference frame with respect to the same probabilistic physical quantity in another probabilistic frame of reference of some other relativistic probabilistic particle now clearly their are two probabilistic reference frame in spacetime in which no difference is present here because both can be considered probabilistically fixed in spacetime and can also be considered to change probabilistically in spacetime(due to changing probabilistic spacetime coordinates or simply change in any probabilistic physical quantity) depending on given situation.

Probabilistic Relativistic Particle

Particle following the Faris' Theory of Special Relativity Probabilistism.

Postulate:3 The Probabilistism's Foundation

When wavefunction collapses upon measurement to the particle form this forbids fluctuation of particle at multiple probabilistic positions or particles travel through wormhole to all positions predicted by probability position function centered at all entangled points of one classical orbit which is seen upon measurement and when it collapses to wave form the quantum decoherence or quantum coherence of particles in atom cause one definite position of daily life objects with small wavelength or just one definite position of daily life objects respectively.

Probabilistism's Foundation

A New Atomic Model is designed. Consider electrons near quarks of nucleus now quarks and electrons are in a quantum state(described by wave function) which will either collapse to wave form of quarks and electrons or to particle form of quarks and electrons.

Case 1 Particle Form

When Particle form observes after measurement then basically what actually happens during measurement is this that the probability of detection of position of one electron will be at many different points before measurement and there exists a instantaneous wormhole between the many positions predicted by position probability function of electron.

Possibility 1

Particles(electrons and quarks) in spacetime foam will go to all positions predicted by probability position function through the instantaneous or fluctuating wormholes. These particles are virtual particles that come out from instantaneous wormhole and enter to the next instantaneous wormhole and instantaneous wormholes are creating and destroying at fixed position, why at fixed position? because of constraint on wavefunction which is because of trap of electron although virtual particles and instantaneous wormholes can exist independently in spacetime as creating and then destroying at any spacetime point but due to trap of electron and constraint on wavefunction in atom instantaneous wormholes and virtual particles behave like this and Yes universe is fluctuating because particles or simply virtual particles first go inside instantaneous wormhole and then comes outside which shows fluctuation. So the concept of fluctuations in matter due to particle's travel in fluctuating wormhole makes an indirect use of concept of virtual particle.

Possibility 2

It is also possible that electron didn't travel through wormhole but actually is a virtual particle fluctuating at fixed place like wormhole again due to its trap in atom but when virtual particle i.e. electron destroys at first probability position where is more entanglement then at the next probability position predicted by probability position function where entanglement field is less and electron will have less entanglement then electron is created their, in this way reach overlap region and then attracted to entangled point and after reaching it goes to other less entangled positions and again transferring through overlap region. These instantaneous wormholes and virtual particles(quarks and electrons) are result of quantum fluctuations in spacetime foam. So **Yes all Universe is fluctuating.**

I am not mathematically very well to predict the right possibility by calculations.

The Uncertainty Principle

In the first possibility when position is known velocity is in wormhole so yes Uncertainty principle preserved even if somehow it will become possible that there is a person outside and a person inside wormhole(which is not possible although) then again Uncertainty Principle is preserved because now electron instead of travelling through wormhole will travel through some higher or lower dimensional hole predicted by string theory and in second possibility before measurement positions are known but there is no velocity present at all only position is changing because virtual particle must be in some other higher or lower dimension although this is not needed in this possibility because since electron and quarks are in trap so yes this version of Uncertainty principle is possible because Uncertainty principle is itself becomes limited due to atom electron and quarks traps and constraints on wave function.

Where does the orbit will be from nucleus and How electron moves?

Considering two parallel universes at left and right of light cone to be quantum entangled it will become easy to know where is electron orbit. This will mean that all particles are entangled to parallel universe particles and there exists points in all classical orbit which are **Entangled Points** (the point in classical orbit at which probability position function is centered). The entangled points is entangled to parallel universe because it contains a virtual particle that is creating and destroying at fixed point and is the one responsible for entangled field and is entangled to the virtual particle in parallel universe at same entangled point. First Entangled Point of a particle in a orbit is that at which first probability position function is centered and at next entangled point in the same orbit the next probability position function is centered and the overlapping in probability position function predicted position is the reason for transfer of electron from one **probabilistic entangled point field** to the next and make electron move in orbit. The orbit will form at some distance from nucleus where there is this entangled point. Measurement is process which makes electron to stop travel through fluctuating wormholes or stop behaving as a virtual particle at multiple

positions predicted by probability position function and become a particle that is moving in classical orbit. The probability position function will predict the positions and at measurement which position dominates radius will form there and the position which will dominate is the entangled point position. Position will dominate where is more entanglement which is entangled point so radius probability function is actually also a shortcut of entangled points of one orbit. Intensity of entangled particle's entanglement i.e. electron due to entangled point field (that is entangled to parallel universe) decreases as it goes to other position probabilities which are far from entangled point position. Bell's Inequality is violated by quantum mechanics at entangled point which shows either realism (particles definite properties before measurement) or locality (information travel faster than light) must be wrong or both must be wrong. So locality is wrong (explained in Problem 2) and realism is also wrong because position changes before measurement.

What happens with quarks? Quarks are also travelling through wormhole and at all positions predicted by probability position function or fluctuating at some multiple positions but the thing is when one quark move from position 1 to 2 another quark moves from position 2 to 1 through wormhole or fluctuation because of less space in nucleus. Their can be one or more electron in fluctuating probabilistic orbit called **Farisian Orbit**. The reason of more space for electron and less for quark is charge exerting electric force.

Case 2 Wave Form

When Wave form is observed after measurement then all the electrons in an atom are waves now these are matter waves described by schrodinger equation these waves are out of sync which means there exists a quantum decoherence between them which cause the definite specific position of objects of daily life but if there will be no decoherence then wavelength of daily life objects can be measured by de broglie wavelength equation, same for quarks.

Some Special Cases

The Probabilistism's Foundation described above is a Complete Case. It is completely possible that in some Atoms the Probabilistism's Foundation did

not hold completely because the wormhole between every position probability can sometimes be missing in such a way that didn't affect calculations, similarly electron does not need to go to every position probability so that these practical things didn't affect calculations. A rough example is **Cutoff Probability Pattern Region**. (explained in The Prediction)

Individual Solution to each Problem

Solution: 1 Laws are different can be same in special cases

Laws are probabilistic and therefore can change depending on which probability dominates.

Solution: 2 New Postulates Without Limitation

New postulates without limitations are made so the postulates of relativity are just now two important random sentences which forms a important theory.

Solution: 3-5 Postulates Are Replaced

Third Problem till Fifth Problem are about postulates which are replaced so problems resolved.

Solution: 6 Theory Of General Relativity Probabilistism

This problem will be resolved in Theory of General Relativity Probabilistism. Although this problem is still partially resolved by changing Relative to Relative Probabilistism.

Solution: 7 BlackMail Physics Loop is still remaining

Seventh Problem is still a Mystery.

Farisian Transformation Equations

Relative Probabilistism quantities means to compare a relativistic probabilistic particle any probabilistic physical quantity in its probabilistic reference frame with respect to the same probabilistic physical quantity in another probabilistic frame of reference of some other relativistic probabilistic particle now clearly their are two probabilistic reference frame in spacetime in which no difference is present here because both can be considered probabilistically fixed in spacetime and can also be considered to change probabilistically in spacetime(due to changing probabilistic spacetime coordinates or simply change in any probabilistic physical quantity) depending on given situation.

How to make these Equations?

Now make two probabilistic reference frames of two relativistic probabilistic particles and compare their probabilistic physical quantities which will make functionally and probabilistically dependent transformation equations.

Mathematical Approach

1. Wormhole Wavefunction

Psi wh (r,t)

Probability density for this wavefunction is a Probabilistic Event function.

2. Virtual Particle Wavefunction

Psi vp (r,t)

Probability density for this wavefunction is a Probabilistic Event function.

3. I don't have enough knowledge to find Entangled Point.

4. Transformation equations

Relation between
P(r,t) and P(r',t')

The Prediction

Consider a Helium atom

When Particle Form Observes

Step 1 Use the mathematics of many electron four dimensional (x,y,z,t) electron traps and insert entangled particles state mathematical data into spacetime geometry of the parallel universe to find out the entangled point.

Step 2 Evaluate probability position function at all entangled points of one classical orbit at a time and also use the mathematics of many electron four dimensional (x,y,z,t) electron traps to set constraints on wavefunction.

Step 3 Find the overlap probabilistic positions by finding out the same numerical values of the probabilistic position function predicted position at all entangled points.

Step 4 Use the calculations of measurement which will collapse it to particle and form a classical orbit to show that how new atomic model collapses to the classical one governed by schrodinger equation.

Step 5 Set quarks as reference in making many electron four dimensional (x,y,z,t) electron traps and apply the same procedure on quarks to find entangled point of quarks possibly located at midpoint of nucleus this will make some pattern in position probability of quark around entangled point if

it is at midpoint of nucleus otherwise there will be some region called **Cutoff Probability Pattern Region** where position probability pattern around nucleus entangled point will collapse.

When Wave Form Observes

Step 1 Use the mathematics of many electron four dimensional (x,y,z,t) electron traps to set constraints on wavefunction of wave of electron.

Step 2 Find resultant wave either zero or not which depends on quantum coherence or decoherence.

Step 3 Although waves are also entangled to parallel universe waves this can also be verified by considering stationary waves in orbits have nodes which are entangled points and can be found as described in particle form prediction of helium atom.

Words

1. Whenever position probability function or probabilistic position function or probabilistic position or position probability type words are used it is definitely at any particular time so to simplify only word position is mentioned instead of event.

2. Whenever word particle is mentioned when discussing before measurement it basically means Relativistic Probabilistic Particle.

Conclusion

Problems in Newton's and Einstein's theory are resolved by using new theory whose postulates are explained. Prediction and New Transformation Equations are presented using the postulates. Mathematical derivations of this theory is a so difficult task that it will need quantum computer and I am also not mathematically very expert but **I will do my best to show everything in this paper mathematically if I get enough knowledge and a Research Team.**

Acknowledgements

"I support Efforts of my Sirs for motivating me in Physics."